

Journal of Geology, Geography and Geocology

Journal home page: geology-dnu-dp.ua

ISSN 2617-2909 (print)
ISSN 2617-2119 (online)

Journ. Geol. Geograph.
Geology,
29(2), 406–414.

doi: [10.15421/112036](https://doi.org/10.15421/112036)

Sergii E. Sardak, Oleksandr P. Krupskyi,
Vladimir Dzhyndzhoian, Margarita Sardak, Yuriy Naboka

Journ. Geol. Geograph. Geocology, 29(2), 406–414.

Development of historical and cultural tourist destinations

Sergii E. Sardak¹, Oleksandr P. Krupskyi², Vladimir Dzhyndzhoian¹, Margarita Sardak³, Yuriy Naboka¹

¹ Dniprovskii University of the Humanities, Dnipro, Ukraine, dnus@ukr.net, dzhyndzhoian@gmail.com, nyvd@ukr.net

² Oles Honchar Dnipro National University, Dnipro, Ukraine, krupskyi71@gmail.com

³ University of Cologne, Köln, Germany, msardak@uni-koeln.de

Received: 25.09.2019

Received in revised form: 14.11.2019

Accepted: 24.04.2020

Abstract. The aim of the study is to develop theoretic and methodological recommendations and practical activities for the positive social, managerial, organizational and economic development of historical and cultural tourist destinations. In theoretical terms: the role of historical and cultural tourist destination in the development of the region has been

established; the historical and cultural tourist destinations have been identified; the author's classification of historical and cultural tourist destinations has been developed basing tourist visiting activeness; the author's methodological approach to the diagnosis and creating tools for development of historical and cultural tourist destinations, comprehensively taking into account resource and factor components, has been presented. In practical terms: variations of the activities aimed at the positive development of historical and cultural tourist destinations have been proposed; the description of measures aimed at the creation of a historical and cultural complex on the example of the designed historical and cultural complex "Stara Samar" has been given. The results of the study are applicable for a wide range of historical and cultural tourist attractions: territories, landscapes and elements of landscapes, historical settlements, parks, film studios, historical and cultural heritage sites, history and culture monuments, burial sites, places of worship, sites of social cultural infrastructure. The author's recommendations provide obtaining commercial results and ensuring a social and cultural effect for businessmen, managers, local communities in the management of existing or in the creation of new historical and cultural tourist destinations.

Keywords: historical and cultural site, tourism, national park, tourist park, monument, factors, resources, activities, Stara Samar

Розвиток історико-культурних об'єктів туристичного призначення

С. Е. Сардак¹, О. П. Крупський², В. В. Джинджоян¹, М. О. Сардак³, Ю. В. Набока¹

¹ Дніпровський гуманітарний університет, Дніпро, Україна, dnus@ukr.net, dzhyndzhoian@gmail.com, nyvd@ukr.net

² Дніпровський національний університет імені Олеся Гончара, Дніпро, Україна, krupskyi71@gmail.com

³ Кельнський університет, Кельн, Німеччина, msardak@uni-koeln.de

Анотація. Завданням дослідження є розробка теоретико-методологічних рекомендацій та практичних заходів позитивного соціального, управлінського, організаційного та економічного розвитку історико-культурних об'єктів туристичного призначення. У теоретичній площині: визначена роль історико-культурних об'єктів туристичного призначення для розвитку регіону; здійснено ідентифікацію історико-культурних об'єктів туристичного призначення; розроблена авторська класифікація історико-культурних об'єктів туристичного призначення, з позиції активності відвідування туристами; представлений авторський методологічний підхід щодо діагностики та розробці заходів розвитку історико-культурних об'єктів туристичного призначення який комплексно враховує ресурсні та факторні складові. У практичній площині: запропоновано варіації заходів спрямованих на позитивний розвиток історико-культурних об'єктів туристичного призначення; наведено характеристику заходів щодо створення історико-культурного комплексу, на прикладі запроєктованого історико-культурного комплексу «Стара Самар». Результати дослідження можуть застосовуватися для широкого кола історико-культурних об'єктів туристичного призначення: території, ландшафти і елементи ландшафтів, історичні поселення, парки, кіностудії, об'єкти історико-культурної спадщини, пам'ятники історії та культури, місця поховань, культові споруди, об'єкти соціокультурної інфраструктури. Авторські рекомендації передбачають отримання комерційних результатів і забезпечення соціально-культурного ефекту для бізнесменів, менеджерів, місцевих громад при управлінні діючими або при створенні нових історико-культурних об'єктів туристичного призначення.

Ключові слова: історико-культурний об'єкт, туризм, національний парк, туристичний парк, пам'ятник, фактори, ресурси, заходи, Стара Самар

Problem statement. Historical and cultural sites are important for society in general and for regions in particular. Firstly, they are an integral organic component of cities, villages and territories, which have already been established and requires permanent maintenance. Secondly, these sites play the role of historical and cultural heritage, which forms the image of the region, its brand and status, as well as serves as an important component in the formation of cultural and national identity of the population. Thirdly, these sites allow the formation of spiritual, cultural and recreational centres of attraction for the local population, migrants and tourists, which leads to the inflow of capital through investment, trade and donations. Thus, historical and cultural sites prolong the life cycle of settlements, countries and civilizations, which is a notable contribution to the social development (Sardak et al, 2019).

In addition, the number of historical and cultural tourist destinations is significant. For example, by the beginning of 2019, UNESCO had registered 1121 World Heritage sites, 869 of which are cultural, 213 are natural and 39 are combined (World Heritage List Statistics).

In the USA, 417 park sites, historical and cultural monuments (60 of which are national parks) make 3.6 % of the national land, the National Park Service (NPS) budget in 2018 was 3.2 billion USD, with the annual visit by more than 277 million people. In addition, there are more than 600 thematic parks and 2100 aqueous entertainment complexes in the United States.

The UNESCO World Heritage List in Canada lists 18 names (as of 2016), what made 1.6 % from the total number of objects. 8 sites are included in the list by the cultural criteria, 1 of them was recognized as a masterpiece of mankind, 10 – by natural indicators, 7 of them were recognized as natural phenomena of exceptional beauty and aesthetic importance. In addition, as of 2016, 6 sites in the territory of the state are among the candidates to be included in the World Heritage List, consisting of 2 – by cultural, and 4 – by mixed criteria (World Heritage List Statistics).

Mexico has 34 UNESCO World Heritage Sites (as of 2016), what makes 3.0 % from the total number. The list includes: 27 cultural sites (13 Pre-Columbian and 15 Post-Colonial era), 6 natural sites, 1 mixed site. 10 of these sites were recognized as masterpieces of human genius and 5 are natural phenomena of exceptional beauty and aesthetic importance. In addition, as of 2016, 22 sites in the state are among the candidates to be included in the World Heritage List, including 11 – by cultural, 5 – by natural and 6 – by

mixed criteria (World Heritage List Statistics).

In Ukraine, there are more than 130 000 fixed monuments of history and culture, 63 historical and cultural reserves (of which are national ones) are in operation, there are 401 historical settlements, 437 state and municipal museums.

In the Russian Federation, the total area of more than 1000 especially protected natural territories makes 7.58 % of the country's territory, 35 of which are national parks, which are visited annually by about 2 million people.

The List of UNESCO World Heritage Sites in India includes 36 items (as of 2017), which is 3.2 % of the total number. 28 sites are included in the List by cultural criteria, 7 objects – by natural, 1 – by mixed criteria. 12 sites were recognized as masterpieces of human creative genius, 3 were recognized as natural phenomena or spaces of exceptional natural beauty and aesthetic importance. In addition, as of 2017, 42 sites in the territory of the state are among the candidates to be included in the World Heritage List Statistics.

Analysis of scientific research and publications.

The study of publications shows that the development of historical and cultural tourist destinations is being actively explored by scientists, international organizations and national services.

For example, the “Global Code of Ethics for Tourism” states that heritage sites should receive funding to maintain, protect, improve and restore them in order to preserve the cultural identity of the nations and nationalities of the Earth, as well as for universal tourist use (Global Code of Ethics for Tourism, 1999).

Floyd (2001) explored the prospects of development parks regarding the racial and ethnic approaches to visiting them. He came to the conclusion that the development of tourism in certain territories (historical and cultural centres) directly depends on multiculturalism and multinationalism of the society. Putrik (2008) in his study considered tourism as a factor in the preservation of historical heritage and the development of the traditions of regions, noting that about 40 % of tourist flows are caused by cultural motivations. Tortora, Randelli and Romei (2014) comprehensively considered the conceptual basis of the study of the region's tourism potential and determined its composition and components.

The New South Wales Government's Report “Cultural landscapes and park management: a literature snapshot” considered the issues of cultural heritage management (Cultural landscapes and park management, 2008). The Report “Cultural Landscapes. A practical guide for park management”

contains the designed guide for park managers to help identify, evaluate, manage and interpret cultural values. Particular attention is paid to the identification and mapping of cultural sites and values (Cultural Landscapes, 2010).

Gonzalez (2011) in his work raised the problem of the lack of any theoretical justification for the creation of cultural parks, taking into account the need for their harmonization between cultural heritage and landscape. He proposed a new theoretical conceptualization of functioning of cultural parks, which serves as the basis of the methodology for empirical research. In the subsequent publication, Gonzalez (2013) considered cultural parks as positive and constructive tools, the effectiveness of which is related to the preservation of heritage, bridging the gap between nature and culture, strengthening identity and memory, and strengthening social cohesion and economic development.

Polyvach (2012) considered the role of cultural heritage and identified its connection with the development of regions. Savranchuk (2013) studied the functional activities and identified the development prospects of the world's leading thematic parks. Düzgüneş and Demirel (2014) studied the potential of national parks for entertainment and tourism events and noted that as a result of their intensive use by visitors, many of them are under threat of destruction. Melgarejo and Gimenez (2015) analyzed the value of the heritage of non-movable and intangible cultural values. A legal analysis of the concept of "cultural park" was performed and it was decided whether it could be applied in the region under consideration. They concluded that the concept of a cultural park was suitable for legal, cultural and environmental purposes. Yang and Chen (2015) in their article addressed the integration of regional culture and urban park to transform the landscape and proposed regional cultural functions that improve strategies for the reconstruction of the landscape of urban parks. Faraci (2017) described the process of forming a sustainable design, social innovation and integration, which was initiated in the restoration and reuse of the abandoned historical centre, which ensured a sustainable identical transformation of this site in a dynamic creative park.

Franch-Pardo, Cancer-Pomar and Napoletano (2017) in their article evaluated the visibility, quality and fragility as the features for determining the protective ability based on both biophysical and visual elements of the landscape. The resulting protection maps can be used to prioritize landscapes for their protection based on their levels of quality and fragility.

Dorofieieva (2017) studied the impact of the existence of cultural and historical heritage sites on the tourist attractiveness of the region. Palinchak, Diachenko and Roshko (2017) reviewed the composition of natural protected areas and sites and focused on the need for their preservation. Biscione, Danese and Masini (2018) demonstrated the need for clear fixation of cultural monuments using the geo-information system (GIS). Such digital cultural heritage map formed the basis for the development of plans to protect, develop and maintain historical and cultural sites. Shafik and El-Husseiny (2019) considered the structure and some guidelines to improve the social support of the area by paraphrasing the park's role in response to the changing needs of the community.

However, the reviewed publications note the following aspects that necessitate further research: an unclear identification of historical and cultural sites; uncertainty of the effective functions of management and economic functions of historical and cultural sites; lack of classification for historical and cultural sites from the point of view of tourists' activeness of visiting them; lack of analysis of the consequences of tourists' visiting historical and cultural tourist destinations; lack of methodological basis for diagnosing the state and development of activities of historical and cultural tourist destinations.

The task of the study. The task of the study is to develop theoretic and methodological recommendations and practical measures for the positive social, managerial, organizational and economic development of historical and cultural tourist destinations.

The study applied the systematic approach, the matrix method, the methods of analysis, synthesis, analogies, abstraction, observation, comparison, grouping, and generalization.

Presentation of the basic material. The considered term "historical and cultural site" is a common name for a very wide range of categories. Thus, in the scientific literature, the legal field of states and the acts of international organizations, historical and cultural sites may imply:

- territory (environmentally guarded territory, natural reserve, natural reserve area, a site of natural reserve fund, historical and cultural reserve, reserve, territorial complex, archaeological territory, etc.);
- landscapes and elements of landscapes (natural territories: coastal zone, spit, beach, lake, river, island and other sites of historical and cultural value);
- historical settlements (areals, cities, villages, settlements, ethnic settlements, etc.);

- parks (cultural park, historical park, historical and cultural park, dendrological park, sites of garden and park art, natural park, memorial park, national park, as well as variations of thematic parks: mega-park, historical park, geographical park, oceanarium, aquapark park of entertainments, safari park, amusement park, space park);
- film studios (Media conglomerates, Majors, Mini-majors, The Studios, Instant major studios, other significant, past independent entities);
- historical and cultural heritage (historical and/or cultural heritage sites: buildings, structures, fortresses, palaces, castles, complexes, ensembles, memorial places, etc.);
- monuments of history and culture (concrete elements: buildings, various architectural forms, neighborhoods, squares, streets, land areas, open undeveloped spaces, memorial signs, etc.);
- burial sites (operating cemeteries, inactive cemeteries, necropolises, mass graves, mounds, graves);
- religious buildings (monasteries, churches, ritual places, mystical structures);
- socio-cultural infrastructure (museums, libraries, archives, etc.).

As it can be seen from the above list, historical and cultural tourist destinations can vary greatly in form, purpose, scale, significance, etc. Accordingly, in the context of the research problem, we will note that an invention of activities on positive development of historical and cultural tourist destinations should be targeted, that is, for each specific site individually.

Therefore, in order to ensure the positive development of historical and cultural tourist destinations, it is advisable to perform their classification. From the point of view of activeness of visiting tourists, historical and cultural sites can be divided into three groups.

The first one includes the sites that are actively protected from tourists (tourists are completely forbidden to visit them and access is allowed only to a limited contingent of persons). For example, according to the International Union for Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (IUCN) classification, it is a “strictly natural reserve” – an area with pristine nature and full protection (IUCN, 2019) or the term “reserve” is used. The world has an estimated 651 biosphere reserves in 120 countries, the largest of which is Pantanal (Brazil) with the area of 195 000 sq. km.

The second one is passively accessible sites (tourists are not forbidden to visit such sites, but special events are not organized for their visits). National and natural parks are included in this category. For example, there are currently 55 national parks in Rus-

sia, their total area of the territory is about 30 million hectares and they are mostly located in the north-west and south of the country. National parks in Europe occupy more than 11 % of the entire area of the continent and their number exceeds 6 000.

The third one is actively accessible sites (tourists are actively involved, the production of tourist reception was created and tourist infrastructure was formed, fees for visits or indirect fees are charged, tours are held, tourist services are rendered). These are the territories where states and private businesses fully or partially fund the use of sites for financial gain (thematic parks, entertainment, cultural, historical centres, etc.). For example, in Germany, the archaeological park, which contains both original and recreated architectural monuments of the Roman town Colonia Ulpia Traiana, operates in the town of Xanten. This is a clear example of how an archaeological reserve, which is an undeniably important historical and cultural monument, but initially not including particularly spectacular objects that can attract both scientists, and tourists, was turned into the largest open-air museum and attracts about half a million visitors annually. Thanks to the regional funding, private investors and philanthropists, large-scale work on experimental archaeology and scientific reconstruction, where history can be touched, tasted and relived by itself were carried out and are still being carried out (LVR-Archaeologisch Park Xanten).

Considering the consequences of visiting historical and cultural destinations by tourists and the connection between such sites and the development of the region, we can note three vectors.

The first is the positive consequences: restoration and support of this destination by tourists (tourists physically do the clearing or repairing on a volunteer basis, allocate targeted funds), the attractions of funds for the development of the tourism infrastructure, employment of the workforce, popularization of the region. Thus, the result of the development of the volunteer movement in the world was the emergence of a new variety in tourism – volunteer tourism. More than 2.5 million people participate in it every year, and revenues are estimated in billions.

The second one is neutral consequences: visiting a historical and cultural site by tourists has any impact neither on the site, nor on the inhabitants of the region of its location. These are mostly the sites that are included in tourist routes as transit (historical buildings and cultural structures visited within long tours, the sites located along the traffic flows between settlements).

The third one is the negative consequences: the

Table 1. The scope of activities aimed at positive development of historical and cultural tourist destinations*

Consequences of visiting Group of sites	Positive	Neutral	Negative
Actively protected	Attraction of volunteers. Creation of real and virtual reconstructions	Reviewing the categories of the tourists who have the right to visit the sites	Restoration of a site. Time limit or complete denial of access for tourists
Passively accessible	Expansion of the geography of tourists. Installation of information stands with schemes and routes of convenient and safe visit of sites. Allocation of funds for creation (improvement) of the infrastructure	Monitoring tourists' visits to the site and controlling possible damage. Introduction of a price policy in the "demand-price-quality" mode	Search and allocation of additional funds to eliminate the negative consequences of visiting sites by tourists (complete or partial repair, restoration)
Actively accessible	Popularization of sites by means of modern methods and tools with the extensive use of social networks, information sources, etc.	Improvement of tourist servicing. Creation of the site's infrastructure	Restriction of the tourists' access to individual objects and facilities. Installation of prohibitive and warning signs (notices), rules of visiting sites. Increased control

* developed by the authors.

destruction of a site by tourists (physical wear, pollution, breakdowns, theft of structural elements). Thus, in the north of England, the defensive fortification of Adrian Wall (it has been a UNESCO World Heritage Site since 1987). It is the part of the popular tourist route, but due to the intensive tourist activity, rains and winds, it is being destroyed and requires urgent recovery. Machu Picchu (Peru) is a mystic town of ancient Indians every year attracts more and more tourists and is gradually taken apart for souvenirs. Cosumel (Mexico) is under the risk to be turned into a real dump because of the desire of tourists to see its beauty. Mogao Grotto (China) is a village that is no longer happy to have tourists, so the local authorities have restricted the access of tourists to prevent the collapse of the existing infrastructure around the attraction.

Based on the consideration of the proposed classification of historical and cultural sites and the consequences of their being visited by tourists, having used the matrix method, we can conceptually outline the scope of activities aimed at the positive development of historical and cultural tourist destinations.

Thus, it should be noted that the development of historical and cultural tourist destinations does not always prioritize an increase in the volume of tourist flows. The measures of the owners of such sites or service organizations should be aimed at forming rational routes, tourists groups, forms of service that correspond to local conditions. This implies increased entrepreneurial activity and cooperation with a wide range of organizations, including: private guides, tour bureaus, travel agencies, tour operators,

museums, hotels, restaurants, service companies, local communities, town halls, university centres, IT companies, advertising agencies, rescue services, TV and radio companies, film industry and other structures.

Having determined the scope of activities aimed at positive development of historical and cultural tourist destination, authorized state authorities, local governments or owners can design the complex of specific actions in relation to the site they service. Methodologically, this may have the following sequence of actions: diagnosis of the factor and resource components; identification of missing resources and necessary changes; development of legally permitted solutions; taking actions; assessments of the result.

Table 2 shows the graphic visualization of the methodological approach to the diagnosis and development of activities on the development of historical and cultural tourist destinations.

The application of this methodological approach involves the identification of systemic factors and resources, and their visual combination in the application of the matrix method, allows inventing the activities for the development of historical and cultural tourist destinations.

Thus, the system factors can be identified as the elements of the environment of the site's location. Therefore, within the natural system, structure-forming elements are natural resources – land, water, and climate. In the format of the biological system, the structure-forming elements are people, animals and plant world. In the technical system, the structure-forming elements are constructions,

Table 2. Methodological approach to diagnosis and development of activities on the development of historical and cultural tourist destinations*

Resources	Human	Material	Non-material	Financial	Temporal
Factors	(H)	(Ma)	(Nm)	(F)	(Te)
Natural (N)	NH	NMa	NNm	NF	NTe
Biological (B)	BH	BMa	BNm	BF	BTe
Technical (T)	TH	TMa	TNm	TF	TTe
Economic (E)	EH	EMa	ENm	EF	ETe
Social (S)	SH	SMa	SNm	SF	STe
Managerial (M)	MH	MMa	MNm	NF	MTe

* developed by the authors based on (Sardak et al, 2017; Sardak et al, 2019).

buildings, roads, technology and machinery. In the economic system, the structure-forming economic elements are sellers, buyers and market infrastructure (including: institutional investors, tour operators and travel agencies, tour offices, farms, shops transport companies, IT companies, advertising agencies, regulatory bodies and other entities). In the social system, the main structure-forming elements are local population, migrants, and tourists. The main managerial structural elements are managers of companies and associations, owners, state authorities and local self-government, associative structures, and international organizations.

From the point of view of management accounting, the following auxiliary tools are used for the development of historical and cultural tourist destinations can be singled out. Human resources are the whole totality of people: those who existed before; prospective (projected, cared for, adaptive, and potentially useful); real; non-prospective (self-sufficient, dependent, out-social); future ones. Material resources are all resources that have a material form: natural resources; spatial-territorial resources; production resources (technological resources, energy resources, material resources, technical resources); highly liquidated physical non-production resources. Non-material resources are auxiliary means not having any material form: intangible resources; information resources. Financial resources are a totality of monetary funds in the cash and non-cash form. Temporal resources are the time used for the development of a site, which can be divided into tactical (operational, operative, short-term, medium-term, long-term) and strategic.

Analysis of the literature review shows that the development of historical and cultural sites is carried out within a number of limited management functions. As a rule, more attention is paid to planning,

organization, and control. However, according to the authors, positive development of historical and cultural tourist destinations in the context of globalization foreseen the permanent application of a wider range of functions, such as: monitoring, diagnostics, forecasting programming, design, modelling, planning, organization, motivation, control, regulation, coordination, information and others.

It should also be noted that the development of historical and cultural sites is carried out within the framework of limited functions of economic activity, first of all: informative-introductory, religious, mystical, entertaining, and economic. However, according to the authors, this is not a complete functional set of commercialization of the socio-economic potential of historical and cultural tourist destinations. Under globalization conditions, the functional set of business activities of the owners of such sites can be expanded by permanently performed functions: creativity (creating legends, developing new concepts of perception of sites, search and opening new sites), intellectualization (increasing the share of the intellectual component during visiting these sites), informatization (popularization of sites, information in effective media and in the Internet, brand formation), recreation (formation of a set of additional conditions and services for recreation, prevention and treatment of tourists), socialization (involvement of tourists in local culture and ethics), spiritual education (introduction of the basics of religious life).

Expanding the scope of management functions and functions of economic activity of historical and cultural sites, as well as their high-quality adapted application, allows achieving a greater effect in key areas of commercialization of historical and cultural sites due to better use of tourist flows:

Table 3. Characteristic of activities on creation the historical and cultural complex “Stara Samar”*

No	Indicator	Characteristic
1	Natural factors (N)	Moderate continental climate, proximity of Dnipro and Samara river basins
2	Biological factors (B)	Limited existence of wild animals not bearing a threat to humans, existence of vegetation (forests, meadows)
3	Technical factors (T)	Remains of a fortress, lack of infrastructure and production enterprises
4	Economic factors (E)	Visiting site for tourists is free of charge
5	Social factors (S)	The site is known among the local population and people interested in historical and cultural monuments
6	Managerial factors (M)	Location on the municipal land
7	Human resources (H)	Targeted labour resources for cleaning and guarding are not allocated
8	Material resources (Ma)	Elements of an old fortress, church, gates, wall, forgery, Kuren (Cossack’s hut)
9	Non-material resources (Nm)	Advertising in social networks, in the Internet, catalogues
10	Financial resources (F)	The site is not funded
11	Temporal resources (Te)	Belongs to the period of 14-17 century A.D., excavation works have been held since 2002
12	Activities NH	Attraction of specialists in archeology, history, geography, geodesics, water and natural resources
13	Activities NB	Control of natural environment state, water resources, green spaces and organizing activities on their optimization
14	Activities NH	Entering information on natural factors of the site into the register, maps and systems
15	Activities NF	Funding of landscaping and keeping the surrounding areas clean
16	Activities NTe	Permanently
17	Activities BH	Attraction of biologists, zoologists, ichtiologists, other specialists
18	Activities BMa	Mounting protective fences, spraying aerosols on the sites and surrounding areas
19	Activities BNm	Entering information on flora and fauna objects in information systems
20	Activities BF	Funding the works on instalment of protective structures and protective activities
21	Activities BTe	Entire period of funding the site
22	Activities TH	Attraction of specialists in construction, architecture, restoration, conservation, reconstruction and landscaping
23	Activities TMa	Fortification of ravines, banks and slopes, reconstruction of structural elements, construction of new structural elements, decoration, construction of technical premises for ensuring the infrastructure operation
24	Activities TNm	Formation of corporative information system
25	Activities TF	Funding of productions and infrastructure development
26	Activities TTe	Site commissioning and operation periods
27	Activities EH	Attraction of specialists to study economic feasibility of investments for construction, restoration, archaeological and recovery works
28	Activities EMa	The development of business plan, receiving and distributing funds. Formation of commodity, price and sales policy. Organization of reception of tourists.
29	Activities ENm	Keeping accounting, tax and statistic records
30	Activities EF	Determining the volume of funding and directions of their distribution
31	Activities ETe	Site commissioning and operation periods
32	Activities SH	Attraction of specialists in history, archaeology, restoration, tour guides, museum teachers, media representatives
33	Activities SMA	Creation of zones for recreation, leisure, entertainment, hygienic premises
34	Activities SNm	Activities on promotion the site in the media, popularization of site. Taking care of cultural heritage and formation of national unity, promoting scientific research and promoting the results of these studies. Organization of tours and field classes in History for children and young people
35	Activities SF	Socialization of the price police for different categories of tourists
36	Activities STE	Permanently
37	Activities MH	Administration of the site and staffing, signing contracts
38	Activities MMA	Development of strategy and tactics. Registration of the site. Administration.
39	Activities MNm	Management, communications, formation of knowledge bases, staff development
40	Activities MF	Staff salary
41	Activities MTe	Site commissioning and operation periods

* developed by the authors

- functional activities (to expand the scope of targets of a site);
- manufacturing activities (transformation of technology for tourist services, application of new equipment, activation of innovatory work of the staff);
- commodity policy (expanding the range of goods and services for tourists: excursions, events, shows, role plays games, quests, sale of souvenirs, photos and videos, accommodation and catering, tasting, attractions, etc.);
- financial policy (redistribution of financing and the structure of financial resources);
- investment policy (change of investment policy, intensification of the search for national and international investors, attraction of loans, attraction of sponsorship, crowdfunding, attracting subsidized financial funds from government agencies and international organizations);
- price policy (change or combination of existing pricing methods and pricing strategies);
- marketing policy (change or expansion of forms of wholesale and retail trade, change of direct marketing forms, use of contractual goods distribution systems (network marketing, franchising, leasing), organization of special forms of market presentation and sale of goods (fairs, exhibitions, commodity exchanges, trading houses, auctions, competitions, tenders), rental provision, online trading);
- promotion (expansion and activation of advertising, public relations activities, marketing promotion and personal actions of staff);
- management and ownership (determining the feasibility of attracting partners, selling part of the shares, establishment of joint ventures);
- management and organization (optimization of the management system, staff replacement, staff development, optimization of the site administration, ensuring staff occupational health and the safety of tourists);
- information support (optimization monitoring, analysis and storage of information storage systems, optimization of paperwork);
- interaction with state authorities and local self-government bodies (establishing long-term contacts, concluding contractual obligations, participation in associating structures, lobbying interests, representation) (Sardak et al., 2019).

For example, the use of the author's methodological approach to the diagnosis and development of historical and cultural tourist destinations, visualized in Table. 2, was carried out during the development of

pre-project proposals for the creation of the historical and cultural complex "Stara Samar" in the city of Dnipro (Ukraine) in 2018. Table 3 provides a brief description of the author's developments.

The data of the studies were considered in the pre-project proposals for the creation of the historical and cultural complex "Stara Samar" on the territory of the national history monument "Novoborogoditska Fortress" and are the basis of the drafted business plan.

Conclusions. The study presents the developed methodology for the positive social, managerial, organizational and economic development of historical and cultural tourist destinations, ensuring: outlining the scope of activities, diagnostics of the factor and resource components, identification of missing resources and necessary changes, making legally allowed decisions, taking actions and assessing the outcome.

The proposed methodological solutions, based on the expansion of the volume of managerial functions and functions of economic activity, are applicable to a wide range of historical and cultural sites and are considered on the example of designing historical and cultural complex "Stara Samar".

Acknowledgement. The article was prepared as a part of the study of pre-project proposals for the creation of the historical and cultural complex "Stara Samar" on the territory of the national historical monument "Novoborogoditska Fortress" commissioned by the Dnipro City Council of the city of Dnipro in Ukraine (Dzhyndzhoian, 2017).

References

- Biscione, M., Danese, M., & Masini, N., 2018. A framework for cultural heritage management and research: the Cancellara case study. *Journal of Maps* 14(2), 576–582. doi: 10.1080/17445647.2018.1517699.
- Cultural Landscapes. A practical guide for park management, 2010. Retrieved from: <https://www.environment.nsw.gov.au/resources/cultureheritage/20100052CulturalLandscapes.pdf>.
- Cultural landscapes and park management: a literature snapshot, 2008. Retrieved from: <https://www.environment.nsw.gov.au/resources/cultureheritage/07137cultlandresearch.pdf>.
- Dorofieieva, K. M., 2017. Analiz vplyvu nayavnosti ob'yektiv kul'turno-istorychnoyi spadshchyny na turystychnu pryvablyvist' rehionu [Analysis of the impact of the cultural and historical heritage objects availability on the touristic attraction of the region]. *Economy and Society*, 13, 184-190 (in Ukrainian).

- Düzgüneş, E. & Demirel, Ö., 2014. Determining the tourism potential of Altındere Valley National Park with respect to its cultural resource values. *International Journal of Biodiversity Science, Ecosystem Services & Management*, 10:4, 322-333. doi: 10.1080/21513732.2014.954143.
- Dzhyndzhoian, V., Repan, O., Teslenko, D., & Ivanytska, O., 2017. Peredproektni propozytyi shchodo stvorennya istoriko-kul'turnoho kompleksu "Stara Samara" na terytoriyi "Novoborodets'koyi fortetsi", pam'yatky vitchyznyanoi istoriyi [Pre-project proposals for the creation of the historical and cultural complex of "Stara Samar" on the territory of the "Novoborodetsky Fortress", a monument of national history]. *Dniprovskii University of the Humanities*, - 180 p. (with drawings) (in Ukrainian).
- Faraci, G., 2017. Farm Cultural Park: an experience of social innovation in the recovery of the historical centre of Favara. *Procedia Environmental Sciences*, 37, 676-688. doi: 10.1016/j.proenv.2017.03.054.
- Floyd, M. F., 2001. Managing National Parks in a Multicultural Society: Searching for Common Ground. *The George Wright FORUM*, 18(3), 41-51.
- Franch-Pardo, I., Cancer-Pomar, L., & Napoletano, B. M., 2017. Visibility analysis and landscape evaluation in Martin river cultural park (Aragon, Spain) integrating biophysical and visual units. *Journal of Maps*, 13(2), 415-424, doi: 10.1080/17445647.2017.1319881.
- Global Code of Ethics for Tourism, 1999. Retrieved from: <http://ethics.unwto.org/en/content/global-code-ethics-tourism>.
- Gonzalez, P. A., 2011. Preserving the future, Projecting the past. What is a Cultural Park? Cambridge: Peterhouse.
- Gonzalez, P. A., 2013. Cultural Parks and National Heritage Areas: Assembling Cultural Heritage, Development and Spatial Planning. Newcastle: Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
- International Union for Conservation of Nature, 2019. Retrieved from: <https://www.iucn.org/>.
- LVR-Archeologisch Park Xanten, 2019. Retrieved from: https://apx.lvr.de/en/willkommen/willkommen_1.html.
- Melgarejo, J., & Gimenez, A. M., 2015. The Cultural and Environmental Enhancement of the Upper Basin of the River Vinalopo in Alicante (Spain). *Historical Industrial Uses of Water: Weirs, Ancient Channels and Water Mills. e-Phaistos*, IV-2, 1-17. doi: 10.4000/ephaistos.771.
- Palinchak, M. M., Diachenko, I. B., & Roshko, S. M., 2017. Klasyfikatsiya pryrodnykh zapovidnykiv ta ob'yektiv u konteksti konventsiyi MSOP ta zakonodavchyykh aktiv Ukrainy [Classification of nature reserves and objects in the context of the IUCN convention and legislative acts of Ukraine]. *Scientific Bulletin of Uzhhorod University. Series "Economics"*, 16(2), 56-60 (in Ukrainian).
- Polyvach, K. A., 2012. Kul'turna spadshchyna ta yiyi vplyv na rozvytok rehioniv Ukrainy [Cultural heritage and its influence on the development of regions of Ukraine]. *Institute of Geography of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine* (in Ukrainian).
- Putrik, Y. S., 2008. Turizm kak faktor sokhraneniya naslediya: istoricheskiy opyt i traditsii [Tourism as a factor of heritage conservation: historical experience and traditions]. *Tomsk State University Journal*, 311, 95-101 (in Russian).
- Sardak, S., 2016. Zhyttyevyy tsykl sotsial'noyi ta ekonomichnoyi system [The life cycle of social and economic systems]. *Marketing and Management of Innovations*, 1, 157-169 (in Ukrainian).
- Sardak, S., Korneyev, M., Simakhova, A., & Bilskaya, O., 2017. Global factors which influence the directions of social development. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 15(3), 323-333. doi: 10.21511/ppm.15(3-2).2017.02.
- Sardak, S. E., Krupskiy, O. P., Korotun, S. I., & Reshetniak, D. E., 2019. Commercialization of the nature-resource potential of anthropogenic objects (on the example of exhausted mines and quarries). *Journal of Geology, Geography and Geoecology*, 28(1), 180-187. doi: 10.15421/111919.
- Savranchuk, L., 2013. Sutnist', hrupuvannya ta perspektyvy svitovoho tematychnoho parku [Essence, grouping and prospects of the world theme park]. *Visnyk of the Lviv University. series geography*, 43(1), 82-91 (in Ukrainian).
- Shafik, Z., & El-Husseiny, M.-A., 2019. Re-visiting the Park: Reviving the "Cultural Park for Children" in Sayyeda Zeinab in the shadows of Social Sustainability. *Journal of contemporary urban affairs*, 3(2), 84-94. doi: 10.25034/ijcua.2018.4704.
- Tortora, M., Randelli, F., & Romei, P., 2014. A Conceptual Framework for Tourism Transition Areas Based on Territorial Capital: a Case Study of Vinci. *J Tourism Hospit* 3, 135. doi:10.4172/2167-0269.1000135
- Yang, X., & Chen, Q., 2015. Study on Relationship between Regional Cultural Heritage and Urban Park Reconstruction. *International Conference on Advances in Energy, Environment and Chemical Engineering (AEECE-2015)*, 541-544.
- World Heritage List Statistics, 2019. Retrieved from: <http://whc.unesco.org/en/list/stat>.